

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND MAGNETIC DATA OF COMPLEXES

Sl. no.	Compd.	Colour	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			μ_{eff} B.M.
			Mo	Br	N	
1.	(5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH ₂) ₂ MoOBr ₅	Brown (crystal)	10.19 (10.72)	42.46 (32.43)	3.0 (2.8)	1.61
2.	(5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH ₂) ₂ MoOBr ₅	Brown (crystal)	8.57 (8.37)	35.70 (36.48)	2.5 (2.7)	1.79
3.	MoOBr ₅ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	12.30 (12.00)	30.76 (30.50)	3.58 (3.70)	1.52
4.	MoOBr ₅ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	10.02 (9.80)	25.05 (24.60)	2.92 (2.78)	1.77
5.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	19.43 (19.39)	32.38 (32.21)	2.88 (2.70)	0.49
6.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	16.46 (16.89)	27.44 (27.85)	2.40 (2.20)	0.28
7.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Cl ₂ -OxineH) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	21.81 (22.06)	19.18 (18.59)	3.18 (3.12)	0.78
8.	Mo ₂ O ₄ Br ₄ (5,7-Br ₂ -OxineH) ₂ ·(H ₂ O) ₂	Brown-black (powder)	18.14 (18.21)	15.12 (15.01)	2.64 (2.70)	0.88

with the experimental results. The two salts, 5,7-dichloro- and 4,7-dibromo-8-hydroxyquinolinium oxopentabromomolybdate(V) show two crystal field transitions¹¹ ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(I)$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_1$ around 14000 and 20000 cm^{-1} and three charge transfer transitions ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2E(II)$, ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2(I)$ and ${}^2B_2 \rightarrow {}^2B_2$ (II) around 25000, 30000 and 37000 cm^{-1} , respectively. About the monomeric complexes *viz.* MoOBr₅-(5,7-Cl₂-OxineH)₂ and MoOBr₅(5,7-Br₂-OxineH)₂, the molecular orbital picture is expected to be different. In this case the number of symmetry elements is expected to be less than that in the case of MoOBr₅²⁻ ion which belongs to C_{4v} point group. But the other distortions from octahedral structure compared to the distortion caused by Mo-O interaction, are expected to be moderate. In this case, there will be a considerable π -interaction with the filled π -orbitals of the ligand and the metal σ -orbitals, as a result the first crystal field transition appears at a lower frequency range around 13000 cm^{-1} than the parent salt. The second crystal field transition appears around 17500 cm^{-1} , and the third one, L→Mo charge transfer around 24000 cm^{-1} . About the dimeric complexes containing Mo₂O₄⁴⁺ and Mo₂O₄²⁺ moiety, tentative assignments of the spectra have been made. No definite conclusion can be drawn because, due to the presence of oxobridge, the identity of the original [MoOBr₅]²⁻ is somewhat lost and so also the molecular orbital picture. However, it has been observed that the first crystal field transition appears around 13600 cm^{-1} , and L→Mo charge transfer band has experienced a red shift and appears around 19000-22800 cm^{-1} in comparison to 24400 cm^{-1} in case of the corresponding mono-meric compound. A similar observation has been made by Mitchell¹². This is presumably due to the fact that in these cases bromine has been replaced by oxygen, a ligand forming stronger bond with metal and thereby destabilising the Mo-L bond to a small extent.

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Azo Complexes. Complexes of Alkali Metal Salts of some Organic Acids with *o*-Nitrobenzene-azo-2-naphthol and *o*-Chlorobenzene-azo-2-naphthol

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In our previous work¹ we have reported the formation of alkali metal adducts with azo ligands, containing electron pushing groups at *o*- and *o'*-positions to the azo group. Now we are reporting the alkali metal adducts formed with ligands which contain electron withdrawing groups at *o*-position to the azo group. We have synthesised the adducts of alkali metal salts of different organic acids with azo ligands NO₂-BAN and Cl-BAN, of the general formulae ML.NO₂-BAN and ML.Cl-BAN, respectively, where M=Li, Na and K; L=deprotonated organic acids; NO₂-BAN=*o*-nitrobenzene-azo-2-naphthol and Cl-BAN=*o*-chlorobenzene-azo-2-naphthol. Analytical data showed that one molecule

of alkali metal salts of organic acids combined with one molecule of the ligand. The ir spectral measurement suggests that NO₂-BAN and Cl-BAN act as a tridentate and bidentate ligands, respectively, towards alkali metals.

Experimental

The ligands NO₂-BAN and Cl-BAN were prepared by standard methods^{2,3}. All the alkali metal salts used were prepared in 95% ethanol.

To the hot absolute ethanolic solution of the ligands, alkali metal salts of organic acids were added in mono-molecular ratio. The whole mixture in solution, was refluxed on a hot-plate using magnetic stirrer for ~2 h. The solution on keeping yielded crystalline adducts. The crystals were filtered, washed with absolute ethanol and dried in an oven at 80°.

Results and Discussion

The azo compounds are stable when stored under dry condition. The adducts are all coloured, either brown or red ; but with NO₂-BAN ligand,

these are more bright. On heating, the adducts decompose at temperatures lower than the melting point of the ligands. ML.Cl-BAN adducts are more soluble in ethanol than ML.NO₂-BAN adducts. The colour, melting or decomposition temperature and analytical results are given in Table 1.

The ligands contain NO₂/Cl and OH groups at *o*- and *o'*-positions to the azo group. Due to the presence of electron withdrawing groups in the *o*-position, the coordinating capacity of N=N may be expected to fall. As such, the adducts have been found to be not that stable. These break up easily on heating to form the simple salts and ligands, suggesting that the bondings are rather weak. It has not been possible to isolate adducts of Cl-BAN ligand with the alkali metal salts of a few organic acids, 2-hydroxy-3-naphthoic acid, salicylic acid, salicylaldehyde, anthranilic acid, while with the respective alkali metal salts, the NO₂-BAN formed isolable adducts.

The variation of coordinating/non-coordinating groups adjacent (in *ortho* position) to the azo group (which already had an OH group in the *ortho* position) in these azo-ligands, causes definite and systematic change in the coordinating ability of

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL AND ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS

Compd.**	Colour	M.p. °C	Analysis % : Found/(Calcd.)			
			O	H	N	M
NO ₂ -BAN(=L)	Red	212	65.50 (65.52)	3.73 (3.75)	14.31 (14.32)	—
Na1N2N.L	Brown	196*	63.64 (63.93)	3.67 (3.48)	10.60 (11.47)	5.04 (4.71)
K1N2N.L	Brown	200*	62.11 (61.90)	3.68 (3.37)	10.34 (11.11)	8.11 (7.73)
Li8HQ.L	Deep red	194*	68.10 (67.80)	3.98 (3.78)	12.11 (12.61)	— (1.57)
Na8HQ.L	Deep red	198*	65.58 (65.22)	3.91 (2.69)	11.89 (12.17)	5.72 (5.00)
NaONP.L	Deep red	194*	58.58 (58.18)	3.65 (3.90)	11.83 (12.33)	5.92 (5.06)
Na2H3NA.L	Deep red	195*	64.85 (64.41)	3.86 (3.58)	7.98 (8.34)	5.05 (4.57)
NaAnth.L	Deep red	197*	61.56 (61.06)	3.96 (3.76)	11.97 (12.39)	5.67 (5.09)
KAnth.L	Deep red	192*	59.12 (58.97)	3.83 (6.63)	11.21 (11.96)	9.01 (8.33)
NaSa1H.L	Deep red	200*	63.76 (63.16)	3.96 (3.66)	9.41 (9.61)	5.87 (5.26)
Cl-BAN=L	Red	165	68.62 (68.65)	3.91 (3.89)	9.89 (9.91)	—
Li1N2N.L	Brown	152*	67.81 (67.60)	3.24 (3.68)	9.52 (9.10)	—
Na1N2N.L	Brown	157*	65.62 (65.34)	3.25 (3.56)	8.98 (8.79)	4.35 (4.81)
K1N2N.L	Brown	158*	63.53 (63.22)	3.21 (3.44)	8.92 (8.51)	7.52 (7.90)
Li8HQ.L	Deep red	150*	69.51 (69.20)	3.71 (3.93)	9.92 (9.68)	—
Na8HQ.L	Deep red	153*	66.43 (66.74)	3.92 (3.78)	9.52 (9.84)	4.98 (5.11)
KONP.L	Deep red	156*	57.25 (57.54)	3.57 (3.26)	9.53 (9.14)	8.12 (8.48)

Decomposition temp.

NO₂-BAN = *o* nitrobenzene-azo-2-naphthol, 1N2N = 1-nitroso-2-naphthol, 8HQ = 8-hydroxyquinoline, ONP = *o*-nitrophenol, 2H3NA = 2-hydroxy-2-naphthoic acid, Anth = anthranilic acid, Sa1H = salicylaldehyde, Cl-BAN = *o* chlorobenzene-azo-2-naphthol.

these ligands towards alkali metals; but these changes in the donor properties are not related in any simple way to the donor group, ring size of the ligand, electro-negativity or polarisability of the metals. They are most likely to be the resultant of some or all of the factors mentioned above.

The present work furnishes a comparative and interesting study of such ligands with those of the ligands of the previous work¹, which formed stabler adducts.

Infrared spectra of ML.NO₂-BAN and ML.Cl-BAN: The ir spectra was recorded in a Perkin-Elmer 521 spectrophotometer with expanded scale. In the adducts, OH stretching frequencies appeared at ~3100 cm⁻¹, which suggests⁴ association of the OH group. The NO₂ asymmetric frequency of the ligand at 1575 cm⁻¹, have been found to be shifted down due to the association⁵ by 5-15 cm⁻¹ in the adducts. The N=N band of the nitro- and chloro-ligands at 1555 and 1570 cm⁻¹, shifted down by 5-20 cm⁻¹ in the adducts, suggesting again the weak⁶ association of N=N group in the adducts. Selected ir frequencies are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—SELECTED IR BANDS

Compd.	$\nu_{as}(\text{NO}_2)$ cm ⁻¹	$\nu_{\text{N=N}}$ cm ⁻¹
NO ₂ -BAN (=L)	1575	1555
Na1N2N.L	1570	1550
K1N2N.L	1565	1545
Li8HQ.L	1570	1550
Na8HQ.L	1565	1550
K8HQ.L	1560	1540
Na2H3NA.L	1570	1540
K2H3NA.L	1570	1550
NaSalA.L	1565	1540
NaSalH.L	1570	1550
Cl-BAN (=L')		1570
Li1N2N.L'		1540
Na1N2N.L'		1555
K1N2N.L'		1540
Li8HQ.L'		1560
Na8HQ.L'		1560

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Solvent Extraction Behaviour of Iron(III) with Versatic 911 and its Application to Indian Minerals

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DURING the last decade considerable progress has been made in the application of solvent extraction to the separation of metals. In this respect high molecular weight carboxylic acids have found considerable interest as extractant in industry, atomic energy programme and in hydrometallurgical processing of ores because of low cost, ease of availability and high metal loading capacity^{1,2}. The synthetic carboxylic acids Versatic 9, Versatic 911 and Versatic 10 have been extensively used in our Laboratory for the extraction of cerium(IV), thorium(IV) and uranium(VI)³⁻⁵. A survey of literature revealed that little work has been done on the extraction of iron(III) with versatic acids^{6,8}. No work has yet been made on the extractive separation of iron from various binary mixtures, moreover, extraction studies has not yet been applied in hydrometallurgy. The present work describes the selective extraction of iron(III) from various metal ions using Versatic 911 as extractant. The study includes the hydrometallurgical separation of iron(III) from a number of available iron mineral.

Experimental

Versatic 911 (Shell Chemical Co., London) is a mixture of tertiary C₉-C₁₁ monocarboxylic acid and its purity is 99% and strength is 5.83 M. Ferric chloride solution (5 mg ml⁻¹) was prepared from ferric chloride (A.R.) and standardised by complexometric titration with EDTA (disodium salt) using sulphosalicylic acid as indicator⁷.

General extraction procedure: The procedure of the experiment was based on the solvent extraction technique. Test solution (10 mg of iron) was taken in a 250 ml separatory funnel and equilibrated with 10 ml Versatic 911 solution (10 ml; Versatic 911-butanol=1:5) by manual shaking. The total volume of the aqueous phase was made up to 20 ml, i.e. the ultimate concentration of iron(III) in the aqueous phase was 8.9×10⁻³ M. The acetate ion concentration was kept at 0.1 M during extraction. The optimum contact time of 5 min was maintained during extraction. After equilibration both the phases were settled for 5 min and the aqueous phase was separated. To remove any trace of organic solvent entrained in the separated aqueous phase, the aqueous phase was washed with butanol (5 ml). The resulting butanol extract was mixed with the separated organic phase. The amount of iron(III) present in the aqueous phase was estimated by complexometric titration. The organic phase was